

TUTORIAL FOR THE DERIVATION OF LIVE-LINE MINIMUM
APPROACH DISTANCES FOR THE 1993 EDITION
OF THE NATIONAL ELECTRICAL SAFETY CODE

PREPARED BY

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July 8, 1993

Chairman, Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers,
Engineering in the Safety, Maintenance, and Operation of
Lines (ESMOL) Subcommittee Working Group on Coordinating
ESMOL Revisions to the National Electrical Safety Code
(NESC) - WG 15.07.07

Chairman, Working Group on Live-Line Clearances - WG 8.1
NESC Subcommittee 8 (SC8) Work Rules

PRESENTED AT

ESMO-93
September 12-17, 1993
Las Vegas, Nevada

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This paper was created to provide the public with the background data for the derivation of the National Electrical Safety Code (NESC) 1993 Edition Minimum Approach Distances. Subcommittee 8 (SC8), Working Rules, used the reasoning and methods of calculation presented here to obtain the published minimum approach distances for NESC-1993. Values in this paper reflect the changes to the Tables and the supporting paragraphs contained in the Tentative Interim Amendment (TIA) to be issued in 1993. *Changes to be reflected in the TIA appear in italic and underlined as shown here.* The Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE) Engineering in the Safety, Maintenance, and Operation of Lines (ESMOL) Subcommittee and the NESC-SC8 agreed to use IEEE Std 4-1978 and Std 516-1987 as the basis for its calculations so that one set of numbers will appear in all documents. These numbers were proposed to OSHA for inclusion in OSHA 1910.269 during the public hearings on that regulation.

The reader is furnished with sufficient data to verify the minimum approach distances. Patience is required to follow the progression for Table 441-1, especially for voltages of 72.5 kV and below. The data was amassed by using six decimal places on the calculator, rounding each calculation in accordance with the principles of Rules 441A5a(1) and 441A5a(2), and reentering the rounded number before performing the next calculation. The respective NESC table appears before the derivation of each table.

Technical assistance was provided by Fred Doering, Jim Gillies, Charley Gross, and Joe VanName. Calculations were made by Hank Kientz and verified by Vivian Kientz.

This document was peer reviewed by the IEEE/ESMOL Working Group on Coordinating ESMOL Revisions to the NESC.

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1. RULES ASSOCIATED WITH USE OF AND DERIVATION OF THE TABLES (1993 NESC)

441. Energized Conductors or Parts

Employees shall not approach, or willingly permit others to approach, any exposed ungrounded part normally energized except as permitted by this rule.

A. Approach Distance to Live Parts

1. General

Employees shall not approach or take any conductive object within the distances to exposed parts which operate at the voltages listed in Table 441-1 or 441-4, and shall not contact exposed energized parts operating at 50 to 300 V, unless at least one of following is met:

- a. The line or part is de-energized.
- b. The employee is insulated from the energized line or part. Insulated electrical protective equipment rated for the voltage involved, such as tools, gloves, or gloves with sleeves, shall be considered effective insulation for the employee from the energized part being worked on.
- c. The energized line or part is insulated from the employee and from any other line or part at a different potential.

2. Precautions for Approach — Voltages from 300 V to 72.5 kV

At voltages from 300 V to 72.5 kV, employees shall be protected from phase-to-phase and phase-to-ground differences in electric potential.

- a. When exposed grounded lines, conductors, or parts are in the work area, they shall be guarded or insulated.
- b. When the Rubber Glove Work Method is employed, rubber insulating gloves, insulated for the voltage involved, shall be worn whenever employees are in the vicinity of energized conductors or parts, supplemented by one of the following two protective methods.
 - (1) The employee shall wear rubber insulating sleeves, insulated for the voltage involved, in addition to the rubber insulating gloves.
 - (2) All exposed energized lines or parts, other than those temporarily exposed to perform work and maintained under positive control, located within maximum reach of the employee's work position, shall be covered with insulating protective equipment.
- c. Cover-up rated for the voltage involved, when used, shall be applied to the exposed facilities as the employee first approaches the facilities from any direction, be that from the structure or from an aerial device, and shall be removed in the reverse order. This protective cover-up shall extend beyond the reach of the employee's anticipated work position or extended reach distance.

3. Transient Overvoltage Control Above 72.5 kV

For voltages above 72.5 kV, the approach distance may be reduced if the maximum anticipated transient overvoltage is known for the worksite. Engineering analysis is required when transient overvoltage control techniques are employed. When preinsertion resistors are employed, they shall be operational. The approach distances derived from Tables 441-2, 441-3, and 441-4 may be used. When a reduced clearance distance from Tables 441-2, 441-3, and 441-4, is used for a specific per-unit transient overvoltage, the maximum transient overvoltage shall be controlled at the worksite by one of the following methods:

- a. The operation of a circuit breaker or other switching device shall be modified, including blocking reclosing.
- b. The overvoltage itself shall be forcibly held to an acceptable level by the installation of temporary transient voltage protective devices, such as surge arresters or temporary protective gaps.
- c. The operation of the system shall be changed to restrict potential overvoltages resulting from the effect of activity on the system (e.g., capacitor switching, tap changing, cable de-energization, etc.).

4. Altitude Correction

The distances in Tables 441-1, 441-2, 441-3, and 441-4 shall be used at elevations below 3000 ft (900 m). Altitude correction factors as indicated in Table 441-5 shall be applied above that altitude. Altitude correction factors shall be applied only to the electrical component of the minimum approach distance.

5. Calculation of Approach Distances

a. Approach distances shown in Tables 441-2, 441-3, and 441-4 are calculated in feet to two decimal places. The second decimal place is rounded up if the third decimal place is other than zero. Because the original rod gap data for voltages from 1.1 to 72.5 kV is measured in metric units, the values in Table 441-1 are derived from metric and converted to feet and inches. The following processes are used:

- (1) When converting to feet and inches, the decimal part of a foot is converted to inches and rounded up if the first decimal place is other than zero.
- (2) When converting from feet to metric, the feet dimension from Rule 441A5a above is converted to meters. The second decimal place shall be rounded up if the third decimal place is other than zero.

- (3) Minimum Approach Distances calculated under this rule for 0.301 to 0.750 kV contain the electric component plus 1.0 ft (0.31 m) for inadvertent movement. Voltages 0.751 to 72.5 kV contain the electric component plus 2.0 ft (0.61 m) for inadvertent movement. Above 72.5 kV, the inadvertent movement distance is 1.0 ft (0.31 m).
- (4) Table 4 (Alternating Current) and Table 5 (Direct Current) of IEEE Std 516-1987 [57] are the electrical basis for approach distances for voltages above 72.5 kV. IEEE Std 516-1987 [57] includes the equation used to derive electrical clearance distances. IEEE Std 4-1978 [53] is the basis for the approach distances for voltages below 72.5 kV.
- (5) The voltage ranges are contained in ANSI C84.1-1989 [51], Table 1. Interpolation between the values contained in Tables 441-2 through 441-4 is not permitted. Approach distances for maximum phase-to-phase voltages other than those contained in Tables 441-2 through 441-4 shall be determined using the process outlined in Rule 441A5a. The approach distances of Table 441-1 shall be used unless the per-unit transient overvoltage is known and controlled.
- b.
- B. Additional Approach Requirements
1. The clear insulation distance associated with insulators shall be the shortest straight-line air-gap distance from the nearest energized part to the nearest grounded part.
 2. When working on insulators under live-line work procedures employing rubber gloves or live-line tools (hotsticks), the clear insulation distance shall not be less than the straight-line distance in air required by Tables 441-1, 441-2, 441-3, and 441-4.
 3. Work may be performed at the grounded end of an open switch if all of the following conditions are met:
 - a. The air-gap distance of the switch shall not be reduced in any manner. This distance shall not be less than the electrical basis for approach distances determined by Rule 441A5a(4) for the maximum anticipated transient overvoltage. The inadvertent movement values of Rule 441A5a(3) are not required in this distance.
 - b. The minimum approach distance to the energized part of the switch shall be not less than that required by Rule 441A.
 4. Special Rules for Working on Insulator Assemblies Operating Above 72.5 kV
 - a. When work is to be performed at the ground end of an insulator assembly, the approach distance to the nearest energized part may equal the straight-line distance measured along the insulators.
 - b. For suspension insulator assembly installations (see ANSI C29.2-1983 [7]) operating above 72.5 kV, the first insulator at the grounded end may be temporarily shorted out as part of the work procedure.
 - c. When performing live-line work employing the bare-hand technique on installations operating above 72.5 kV, the first insulator at the energized (hot) end of a suspension insulator assembly (see ANSI C29.2-1983 [7]) may be shorted out during the work.
 - (1) The approach distance to the grounded end of the insulator assembly may be equal to the straight-line distance from the nearest energized part to the closest grounded part across the insulators.
 - (2) The straight-line insulation distance shall be not less than the values required by Tables 441-1, 441-2, 441-3, and 441-4.
- C. Live-Line Tool Clear Insulation Length
1. Clear Live-Line Tool Length. The clear live-line tool distance shall be not less than the distance measured longitudinally along the live-line tool from the conductive part at the working end of the tool and any part of the employee. Distances for conducting sections (such as metallic splices and hardware) shall be subtracted from the clear live-line length. The clear live-line tool length shall equal or exceed the values for the minimum approach distance in Tables, 441-1, 441-2, 441-3, and 441-4 for the indicated voltage ranges. The minimum clear live-line tool distance shall be the distance measured longitudinally along the live-line tool from the conductive part at the working end of the tool to any part of the employee.
 2. Live-Line Conductor Support Tool Length
Conductor support tools such as link sticks, strain carriers, and insulator cradles may be used provided that the clear insulating distance is at least as long as the insulator string or the maximum distance specified in Rule 441A. When installing this equipment, the employee shall maintain the approach distance required equal to the clear insulating length for the support tools.
- NOTE: Conductive components of tools disturb the field in the gap and decrease the insulation value of the tool more than the linear subtraction of the length(s) of the conductive components.

2. DERIVATION OF Table 441-1

Table 441-1 AC Live-Line Work Minimum Approach Distance
Distance to Employee

Voltage in kilovolts phase-to-phase	Phase-to-Ground		Phase-to-Phase	
	(ft-in)	(m)	(ft-in)	(m)
0 to 0.050*	Not Specified		Not Specified	
0.051 to 0.300*	Avoid Contact		Avoid Contact	
0.301 to 0.750±	1- 0	0.31	1- 0	0.31
0.751 to 15.0	2- 2	0.65	2- 3	0.67
15.1 to 36.0	2- 7	0.77	2-10	0.86
36.1 to 46.0	2- 9	0.84	3- 2	0.96
46.1 to 72.5	3- 3**	1.00	3-11	1.20
72.6 to 121	3- 2**	0.95	4- 3	1.29
138 to 145	3- 7	1.09	4-11	1.50
161 to 169	4- 0	1.22	5- 8	1.71
230 to 242	5- 3	1.59	7- 6	2.27
345 to 362	8- 6	2.59	12- 6	3.80
500 to 550	11- 3	3.42	18- 1	5.50
765 to 800	14-11	4.53	26- 0	7.91

* For single phase systems, use the voltage to ground.

** The 46.1 to 72.5 kV phase-to-ground 3- 3 distance contains a 1- 3 electrical component and a 2- 0 inadvertent movement component while the 72.6 to 121 kV phase-to-ground 3- 2 distance contains a 2- 2 electrical component and a 1- 0 inadvertent movement component. In other words, these values are correct.

DERIVATION OF Table 441-1. AC PHASE-TO-GROUND
MINIMUM APPROACH DISTANCES IN FEET AND INCHES

0 kV to 72.5 kV Calculations (Voltages are phase-to-phase unless otherwise noted) NOTE: The number of significant digits used throughout these calculations are used to support rounding in each column in accordance with Rules 441A5a(1) and 441A5a(2).

TABLE A

(1) Voltage Range (kV)	(2) Gap Distance (in)	(3) Integer Inches (in)	(4) Inadvertent Movement Adder (ft)	(5) Table Distance (ft-in)
0.0 to 0.050*	----	--	----Not Specified----	
0.051 to 0.300*	----	--	----Avoid Contact----	
0.301 to 0.750*	**	**	1	1- 0
0.751 to 15.0	1.47	2	2	2- 2
15.1 to 36.0	6.28	7	2	2- 7
36.1 to 46.0	8.95	9	2	2- 9
46.1 to 72.5	15.07	15	2	3- 3

* For single phase systems, use the voltage to ground.

** Use inadvertent movement adder only.

Where:

Column (1): Voltage Range (ANSI Std C84.1-1989, Table 1).

Column (2): Gap distance (gap = electrical distance) in cm calculated from ANSI/IEEE Std 4-1978, Appendix 2B as follows:

TABLE B

(a) Voltage Range (kV)	(b) TOV (pu)	(c) Maximum Operating Voltage Voltage (kV-RMS)	(d) Maximum Overvoltage Voltage (kV-Crest)	(e) Maximum Overvoltage Plus 3 σ (kV-Crest)
0.050*	Values of surges on the 0.050 to 0.750 kV			
0.300*	single phase voltage range do not influence			
0.750*	the minimum approach distances.			
15.0	3	25.9808	36.7424	43.2264
36.0	3	62.3539	88.1818	103.7433
46.0	3	79.6744	112.6767	132.5609
72.5	3	125.5737	177.5881	208.9272

* For single phase systems, use the voltage to ground.

Where the minimum approach distances in cm are derived as follows:

Column (a): Maximum phase-to-phase voltage within the range.

Column (b): Transient overvoltage (TOV) of 3.0 per-unit (pu). International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC), Technical Committee Number 78 (TC78) (Tools For Live-line Working), Working Group (WG) 2 (Rigid Insulating Devices) along with Working Group 3 (Flexible Insulating Devices) agreed in Toronto in June 1990, to use a maximum transient overvoltage of 3.0 pu phase-to-ground when testing tools and equipment and to state that the 3.0 pu is used in their documents. All systems having overvoltages above the 3.0 pu should take this limiting value into account.

Column (c): The maximum voltage in RMS is Column (a) kilovolts divided by square root of 3 times the per-unit value of Column (b) or $[(\text{Column (a)})/(3^{1/2})](\text{Column (b)})$.

Column (d): The Maximum overvoltage crest is Column (c) times square root of 2 or $(\text{Column (c)})(2^{1/2})$. NOTE - FOR VALUES FROM 15.0 KV TO 72.5 KV: IEC TC78 (Secretariat) 51, October 1991, Guidelines For Dielectric Testing For Tools and Equipment, still under review, does not provide a precise value for the ratio of impulse crest-to-power frequency test value. As an example, where the air gap is similar to that found in service, the maximum transient overvoltage values for this voltage range is 3.0 pu, resulting in a maximum crest voltage calculated by the equation $(\text{Column (c)}) \times \text{square root of 2 divided by 1.3}$ or $[(\text{Column (c)})(2^{1/2})]/1.3$. Note that the 1.3 factor is not used in testing in the voltage ranges 72.5 kV and below, as these ranges were not included in the background testing, and further the air clearances are so small they are not significant when determining approach distances. THE 1993 EDITION OF THE NESC IS BASED ON AIR GAP DISTANCES AND THEREFORE, THESE TABLES DO NOT INCLUDE THE 1.3 FACTOR.

Column (e): The maximum overvoltage for plus 3 sigma (commonly taken to be 15%), 60 Hertz crest, is Column (d) times 1 over (100% - 15%) or $(\text{Column (d)})(1/0.85)$. NOTE: Sigma = 5%, 3 sigma = 15%.

The voltages from column (e) above are interpolated from the following Table (portion of Table 2B.1 from ANSI/IEEE Std. 4-1978) providing the basis for voltages from 15.0 kV to 72.5 kV. The test data was in centimeters, therefore the feet and inches are calculated from centimeters to minimize rounding differences.

TABLE C
Portion of ANSI Std 4-1978 Table 2B.1

Rod-Gap Sparkover Alternating Crest Voltage (*) (**)			
Gap Spacing (cm)	60 Hz kV Crest	Gap Spacing (cm)	60 Hz kV Crest
2	25	14	95
3	36	16	104
4	46	18	112
5	53	20	120
6	60	25	143
8	70	30	167
10	79	35	192
12	86	40	218

* Sparkover values are for two one-half-inch square rod electrodes, each cut off squarely and mounted horizontally on supports so that a length of rod equal to or greater than one-half the gap spacing overhangs the inner edge of the support. The height of the rods above the ground plane should be at least 1.3 times the gap spacing plus 4 inches. Sparkover values are for standard atmospheric conditions. The accuracy in rod gap sparkover voltage can be as large as plus or minus 8%.

** The above values differ slightly from the values based on AIEE #4-1943. This is due to using a 20° C standard temperature rather than a 25° C standard, and because the 1943 Table contained less data points. This in turn had required a curve to be fit to the data, rather than permitting simple linear interpolation.

The interpolation equation chosen for ratios in the matrix

$$\begin{vmatrix} A & a \\ B & b \\ C & c \end{vmatrix}$$

is $\frac{B-A}{C-A} = \frac{b-a}{c-a}$, the calculations become:

TABLE D

Matrix		Ratio Equation	Gap Spacing for Column (e) above	
Crest (kV)	Gap (cm)		(cm)	(m)
36	3	$\frac{43.2264 - 36}{46 - 36} = \frac{X - 3}{4 - 3}$	or X = 3.7227	0.03723
43.2264	X			
46	4			
95	14	$\frac{103.7433 - 95}{104 - 95} = \frac{X - 14}{16 - 14}$	or X = 15.9430	0.15943
103.7433	X			
104	16			
120	20	$\frac{132.5609 - 120}{143 - 120} = \frac{X - 20}{25 - 20}$	or X = 22.7307	0.22731
132.5609	X			
143	25			
192	35	$\frac{208.9272 - 192}{218 - 192} = \frac{X - 35}{40 - 35}$	or X = 38.2553	0.38256
208.9272	X			
218	40			

The conversion of meters to inches is as follows:

TABLE E

(a) Voltage Range (kV)	(b) Gap (m)	(c) Gap (ft)	(d) Gap (in)
0.751 to 15.0	0.03723	0.12215	1.4658
15.1 to 36.0	0.15943	0.52306	6.2768
36.1 to 46.0	0.22731	0.74576	8.9492
46.1 to 72.5	0.38256	1.25511	15.0614

Where:

Column (a): Voltage Range (ANSI Std C84.1, Table 1).

Column (b): Gap in meters from the above interpolations.

Column (c): Meters from Column (b) times 3.2808 feet/meter equal gap in feet.

Column (d): Decimal portion (ONLY) of Column (c) in feet times 12 inches/foot plus integer feet in inches. Column (d) decimal inches rounded in accordance with Rule 441A5a(1) plus integer feet equal the decimal inch values for Column (2).

Column (3): Column (d) rounded in accordance with Rule 441A5a(1).

Column (4): Inadvertent movement (ergonomic) adder in accordance with Rule 441A5a(3). NOTE: The 2 ft inadvertent movement adder for voltages 0.751 to 72.5 kV is taken from the October 30-31, 1991 minutes of the NESC Subcommittee 8 (SC8), Work Rules, in the formulation of the 1993 Edition. System conditions for this range are not predictable or controllable enough to use the 1 ft adder specified for voltages above 72.5 kV. The 1 ft adder for 0.301 to 0.750 kV is based on industry practices for this voltage range.

Column (5): Column (3) plus Column (4) in feet and inches equal values in Table 441-1.

TABLE F

(1) Voltage Range (kV)	(2) Gap Distance (ft)	(3) Decimal Feet to Inches (in)	(4) Integer Inches (in)	(5) Feet Plus Inches (ft-in)	(6) Inadvertent Movement Adder (ft)	(7) Table Distance (ft-in)
72.6 to 121	2.10	1.20	2	2- 2	1	3- 2
138 to 145	2.55	6.60	7	2- 7	1	3- 7
161 to 169	3.00	0.00	0	3- 0	1	4- 0
230 to 242	4.20	2.40	3	4- 3	1	5- 3
345 to 362	7.48	5.76	6	7- 6	1	8- 6
500 to 550	10.21	2.52	3	10- 3	1	11- 3
765 to 800	13.86	10.32	11	13-11	1	14-11

Column (1): Voltage Range (ANSI Std C84.1-1989, Table 1).

Column (2): Gap distance (IEEE Std 516-1987 Table 4 (Feet)). Technical information for United States electrical systems indicates that present design provide maximum per-unit transient overvoltage values (eg. produced by switching surges, capacitor switching, etc.) of 3.0 pu for 362 kV and below, 2.4 pu for 550 kV, and 2.0 pu for 800 kV.

Column (3): Decimal portion (ONLY) from Column (2) times 12 inches/foot equal decimal inches.

Column (4): Column (3) rounded in accordance with Rule 441A5a(1).

Column (5): Integer feet from Column (2) plus integer inches from Column (4).

Column (6): Inadvertent movement (ergonomic) adder in accordance with Rule 441A5a(3). NOTE: The 1 ft inadvertent movement adder for voltages 72.6 to 800 kV is taken from the October 30-31, 1991 minutes of the NESC Subcommittee 8 (SC8), Work Rules, in the formulation of the 1993 Edition. System conditions for this range do not require additional distances.

Column (7): Column (5) plus Column (6) in feet and inches equal values in Table 441-1.

**DERIVATION OF Table 441-1, AC PHASE-TO-GROUND
MINIMUM APPROACH DISTANCES IN METERS**

0 kV to 72.5 kV Calculations (Voltages are phase-to-phase unless otherwise noted)

TABLE G

(1) Voltage Range (kv)	(2) Gap Distance (m)	(3) Inadvertent Movement Adder (m)	(4) Calculated Distance (m)	(5) Table Distance (m)
0.0 to 0.050*	-----	-----	Not Specified-----	
0.051 to 0.300*	-----	-----	Avoid Contact-----	
0.301 to 0.750*	**	0.3048	0.3048	0.31
0.751 to 15.0	0.03723	0.6096	0.6469	0.65
15.1 to 36.0	0.15943	0.6096	0.7691	0.77
36.1 to 46.0	0.22731	0.6096	0.8370	0.84
46.1 to 72.5	0.38256	0.6096	0.9922	1.00

* For single phase systems, use the voltage to ground.

** Use inadvertent movement adder only.

Where:

Column (1): Voltage Range (ANSI Std C84.1-1989, Table 1).

Column (2): Electric distance (gap) in meters from the above interpolations, TABLE E, Column (b).

Column (3): Inadvertent movement (ergonomic) adder in accordance with Rule 441A5a(3).

Column (4): Column (2) plus Column (3).

Column (5): Column (4) rounded in accordance with Rule 441A5a(2) in meters equal values in Table 441-1.

TABLE H

(1) Voltage Range (kV)	(2) Gap Distance (ft)	(3) Feet to Meters (m)	(4) Inadvertent Movement Adder (m)	(5) Calculated Distance (m)	(6) Table Distance (m)
72.6 to 121	2.10	0.6401	0.3048	0.9449	0.95
138 to 145	2.55	0.7773	0.3048	1.0821	1.09
161 to 169	3.00	0.9144	0.3048	1.2192	1.22
230 to 242	4.20	1.2802	0.3048	1.5850	1.59
345 to 362	7.48	2.2799	0.3048	2.5847	2.59
500 to 550	10.21	3.1120	0.3048	3.4168	3.42
765 to 800	13.86	4.2246	0.3048	4.5294	4.53

Where:

Column (1): Voltage Range (ANSI Std C84.1-1989, Table 1).

Column (2): Gap distance (See TABLE F, Column (2)).

Column (3): Feet from Column (2) times 0.3048 meters/foot equal the distance in meters.

Column (4): Inadvertent movement (ergonomic) adder in accordance with Rule 441A5a(3).

Column (5): Column (3) plus Column (4) equal calculated approach distance.

Column (6): Column (5) rounded in accordance with Rule 441A5a(2) in meters equal the values in Table 441-1.

Table 441-1. AC PHASE-TO-PHASE MINIMUM APPROACH DISTANCES

Phase-to-Phase Transient Overvoltage Multipliers

Phase-to-phase switching surge strength is a complicated phenomenon because there can be a time displacement between the surges on parallel conductors and the ratio of the positive and negative on the two electrodes may vary. The time displacement may cause the maximum voltage between phases to be less than the sum of the phase-to-ground voltages. The CIGRE Study Committee 33-07 on phase-to-phase insulation coordination suggests an approximate relationship between phase-to-ground and phase-to-phase switching surge overvoltage magnitudes based on the per-unit of system phase-to-ground crest as published in ELECTRA, Vol 149, December 1992. The relationship appears in the Electric Power Research Institute (EPRI) Bluebook, Transmission Line Reference Book, 115-138 kV Compact Line Design, Section 5, Insulation For Switching Surges, Figure 5.2. The relationship given in EPRI Figure 5.2 (Figure 1 this document) has been converted into two equations as follows:

1. Derive Equations from the Figure 1 Graph to determine the ratio of "per-unit phase-to-ground maximum switching surge" (x-axis) to "per-unit phase-to-phase maximum switching surge" (y-axis). Using equations:

$$\text{Eq 1. } m = (y_2 - y_1)/(x_2 - x_1),$$

$$\text{Eq 2. } y = mx + b,$$

$$\text{Eq 2a. } b = y - mx, \text{ and}$$

$$\text{Eq 2b. } y = mx + b.$$

2. Phase-to-ground per-unit values of 1.5 to 2.0. From the graph, use $y_1 = 2.25$, $y_2 = 3.6$, $x_1 = 1.6$, and $x_2 = 2.0$. The equations become:

$$\text{(Eq 1) } m = (3.6 - 2.25)/(2.0 - 1.6) = 3.3750 \text{ and}$$

$$\text{using, } y_2 = 3.6, \text{ and } x_2 = 2.0,$$

$$\text{(Eq 2a) } b = 3.6 - (3.3750)(2.0) = -3.15$$

then, for any given x,

$$\text{(Eq 2b) } y = (3.3750)x - 3.1500$$

3. Phase-to-ground per-unit values of 2.0 to 3.0. From the graph, use $y_1 = 3.6$, $y_2 = 4.6$, $x_1 = 2.0$, and $x_2 = 3.0$. The equations become:

$$\text{(Eq 1) } m = (4.6 - 3.6)/(3.0 - 2.0) = 1.0 \text{ and}$$

$$\text{using, } y_2 = 4.6, \text{ and } x_2 = 3.0,$$

$$\text{(Eq 2a) } b = 4.6 - (1.0)(3.0) = 1.6$$

then, for any given x,

$$\text{(Eq 2b) } y = (1.0)x + 1.6$$

Phase-to-phase values for Column (1) below are obtained by using the above equations with the x values of Column (2). Column (3) is the ratio of Column (1) divided by Column (2). Column (4) is the multiplier used in each of the following phase-to-phase tables.

TABLE I

(1) Phase-to-Phase (pu)	(2) Phase-to-Ground (pu)	(3) Ratio	(4) Multiplier
1.9125	1.5	1.9125/1.5	1.2750
2.2500	1.6	2.2500/1.6	1.4063
2.5875	1.7	2.5875/1.7	1.5221
2.9250	1.8	2.9250/1.8	1.6250
3.2625	1.9	3.2625/1.9	1.7171
3.6000	2.0	3.6000/2.0	1.8000
3.7000	2.1	3.7000/2.1	1.7619
3.8000	2.2	3.8000/2.2	1.7273
3.9000	2.3	3.9000/2.3	1.6957
4.0000	2.4	4.0000/2.4	1.6667
4.1000	2.5	4.1000/2.5	1.6400
4.2000	2.6	4.2000/2.6	1.6154
4.3000	2.7	4.3000/2.7	1.5926
4.4000	2.8	4.4000/2.8	1.5715
4.5000	2.9	4.5000/2.9	1.5518
4.6000	3.0	4.6000/3.0	1.5334

**DERIVATION OF Table 441-1. AC PHASE-TO-PHASE
MINIMUM APPROACH DISTANCES IN FEET AND INCHES**

0 kV to 72.5 kV Calculations (Voltages are phase-to-phase unless otherwise noted)

TABLE J

(1) Voltage Range (kV)	(2) Gap Distance (m)	(3) Ratio	(4) Phase-to-Phase (m)	(5) Phase-to-Phase (ft)	(6) Integer Inches (in)	(7) Inadvertent Movement Adder (ft)	(8) Table Distance (ft-in)
0.0 to 0.050*	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----Not Specified-----	
0.051 to 0.300*	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----Avoid Contact-----	
0.301 to 0.750*	**	**	**	**	**	1	1- 0
0.751 to 15.0	0.03723	1.5334	0.05709	0.1873	3	2	2- 3
15.1 to 36.0	0.15943	1.5334	0.24447	0.8021	10	2	2-10
36.1 to 46.0	0.22731	1.5334	0.34856	1.1436	14	2	3- 2
46.1 to 72.5	0.38256	1.5334	0.58662	1.9246	23	2	3-11

* For single phase systems, use the voltage to ground.

** Use inadvertent movement adder only.

Where:

Column (1): Voltage Range (ANSI Std C84.1-1989, Table 1).

Column (2): Gap distance in meters (Table E, Column (b)).

Column (3): Ratio multiplier from Table I.

Column (4): Column (2) times Column (3).

Column (5): Column (4) times 3.2808 feet/meter equal gap in feet.

Column (6): Decimal portion (ONLY) of Column (5) in feet times 12 inches/foot plus integer feet in inches. Rounded in accordance with Rule 441A5a(1) equal integer inches.

Column (7): Inadvertent movement (ergonomic) adder in accordance with Rule 441A5a(3).

Column (8): Column (6) plus Column (7) in feet and inches equal values in Table 441-1.

TABLE K

(1) Voltage Range (kV)	(2) *Gap Distance (ft)	(3) Ratio	(4) Phase-to- Phase (ft)	(5) Decimal Inches (in)	(6) Integer Inches (in)	(7) Calculated Distance (ft-in)	(8) Table Distance (ft-in)
72.6 to 121	2.10	1.5334	3.2202	2.6424	3	3- 3	4- 3
138 to 145	2.55	1.5334	3.9102	10.9224	11	3-11	4-11
161 to 169	3.00	1.5334	4.6002	7.2024	8	4- 8	5- 8
230 to 242	4.20	1.5334	6.4403	5.2836	6	6- 6	7- 6
345 to 362	7.48	1.5334	11.4699	5.6388	6	11- 6	12- 6
500 to 550	10.21	1.6667	17.0170	0.2040	1	17- 1	18- 1
765 to 800	13.86	1.8000	24.9480	11.3760	12	25- 0	26- 0

* Transient Overvoltages are 3.0 pu except for 2.4 pu at 500 kV to 550 kV and 2.0 at 765 kV to 800 kV.

Where:

Column (1): Voltage Range (ANSI Std C84.1-1989, Table 1).

Column (2): Gap distance (See TABLE F, Column (2)).

Column (3): Ratio multiplier from TABLE I.

Column (4): Column (2) times Column (3).

Column (5): Decimal portion (ONLY) of Column (4) times 12 inches/foot equal decimal inches.

Column (6): Column (5) rounded in accordance with Rule 441A5a(1).

Column (7): Integer feet from Column (4) plus integer inches from Column (6).

Column (8): Column (7) plus 1 foot inadvertent movement (ergonomic) adder in accordance with Rule 441A5a(3) in feet and inches equal values in Table 441-1.

**DERIVATION OF Table 441-1. AC PHASE-TO-PHASE
MINIMUM APPROACH DISTANCES IN METERS**

0 kV to 72.5 kV Calculations (Voltages are phase-to-phase unless otherwise noted)

TABLE L

(1) Voltage Range (kV)	(2) Gap Distance (m)	(3) Inadvertent Movement Adder (m)	(4) Calculated Distance (m)	(5) Table Distance (m)
0.0 to 0.050*	-----	-----	Not Specified-----	
0.051 to 0.300*	-----	-----	Avoid Contact-----	
0.301 to 0.750*	**	0.3048	0.3048	0.31
0.751 to 15.0	0.05709	0.6096	0.6667	0.67
15.1 to 36.0	0.24447	0.6096	0.8541	0.86
36.1 to 46.0	0.34856	0.6096	0.9582	0.96
46.1 to 72.5	0.58662	0.6096	1.1963	1.20

* For single phase systems, use the voltage to ground.

** Use inadvertent movement adder only.

Where:

Column (1): Voltage Range (ANSI C84.1-1989, Table 1).

Column (2): Gap distance from TABLE J, Column (4).

Column (3): Inadvertent movement (ergonomic) adder in accordance with Rule 441A5a(3).

Column (4): Column (2) plus Column (3).

Column (5): Column (4) rounded in accordance with Rule 441A5a(2) in meters equal values in Table 441-1.

72.6 to 800 kV Calculations (Voltages are phase-to-phase unless otherwise noted)

TABLE M

(1) Voltage Range (kV)	(2) *Gap Distance (ft)	(3) Feet to Meters (m)	(4) Inadvertent Movement Adder (m)	(5) Calculated Distance (m)	(6) Table Distance (m)
72.6 to 121	3.2202	0.9816	0.3048	1.2864	1.29
138 to 145	3.9102	1.1919	0.3048	1.4967	1.50
161 to 169	4.6002	1.4022	0.3048	1.7070	1.71
230 to 242	6.4403	1.9630	0.3048	2.2678	2.27
345 to 362	11.4699	3.4961	0.3048	3.8009	3.80
500 to 550	17.0170	5.1868	0.3048	5.4916	5.50
765 to 800	24.9480	7.6042	0.3048	7.9090	7.91

* Transient Overvoltages are 3.0 pu except for 2.4 pu at 500 kV to 550 kV and 2.0 at 765 kV to 800 kV (See TABLE F, Column (2)).

Where:

- Column (1): Voltage Range (ANSI C84.1-1989, Table 1).
- Column (2): Gap Distance from TABLE K, Column (4).
- Column (3): Column (2) times 0.3048 meters/foot.
- Column (4): Inadvertent movement (ergonomic) adder in accordance with Rule 441A5a(3).
- Column (5): Column (3) plus Column (4).
- Column (6): Column (5) rounded in accordance with Rule 441A5a(2) in meters equal values in Table 441-1.

3. DERIVATION OF Table 441-2 AND TABLE 441-3

The voltages from the ranges 121 kV to 800 kV are top of the range voltages specified in ANSI Std C84.1-1982. Interpolation between table voltages is not permitted (Rule 441A5b). Calculations must be performed in accordance with Rule 441A5a(4) and the equations and criteria of IEEE Std 516-1987. A sample calculation requiring interpolation is presented in EXAMPLE 2.

Approach distances may be reduced when system operating conditions are known and controlled (Rule 441A3 "For voltages above 72.5 kV, the approach distance may be reduced if the maximum anticipated transient overvoltage is known for the worksite. Engineering analysis is required when transient overvoltage control techniques are employed."). Also, Rule 441A5a(4) references IEEE Std 516-1987 equations and criteria for reduced clearances with transient overvoltage control using devices such as worksite personal protective gaps. Worksite transient overvoltage system(s) (e.g., personal protective gaps) shall be designed and tested by qualified engineers prior to employment of the personal protective gap.

Transient overvoltage ranges are in accordance with the TABLE F, Column (2) explanation.

**DERIVATION OF Table 441-2 FT. AC PHASE-TO-GROUND
PER-UNIT DISTANCES IN FEET AND INCHES**

**Table 441-2 FT
AC Live-Line Work Minimum Approach Distance
With Transient Overvoltage Factor**

Maximum Anticipated Per-Unit Transient Over-Voltage	Distance to Employee In Feet-Inches, <u>Phase-To-Ground</u>						
	Air, Bare-Hand, and Clear Live-Line Tool						
	Maximum Phase-to-Phase Voltage In Kilovolts						
	<u>121</u>	<u>145</u>	<u>169</u>	<u>242</u>	<u>362</u>	<u>550</u>	<u>800</u>
1.5						6- 0	9- 8
1.6						6- 6	10- 8
1.7						7- 0	11- 8
1.8						7- 7	12- 8
1.9						8- 1	13- 9
2.0	2- 5	2- 9	3- 0	3-10	5- 3	8- 9	14-11
2.1	2- 6	2-10	3- 2	4- 0	5- 5	9- 4	
2.2	2- 7	2-11	3- 3	4- 1	5- 9	9-11	
2.3	2- 8	3- 0	3- 4	4- 3	6- 1	10- 6	
2.4	2- 9	3- 1	3- 5	4- 5	6- 4	11- 3	
2.5	2- 9	3- 2	3- 6	4- 6	6- 8		
2.6	2-10	3- 3	3- 8	4- 8	7- 1		
2.7	2-11	3- 4	3- 9	4-10	7- 5		
2.8	3- 0	3- 5	3-10	4-11	7- 9		
2.9	3- 1	3- 6	3-11	5- 1	8- 2		
3.0	3- 2	3- 7	4- 0	5- 3	8- 6		

121 kV, 2.0 through 3.0 pu Transient Overvoltage

TABLE N-1

(1) Per-Unit TOV	(2) Gap Distance (ft)	(3) Decimal Feet to Inches (in)	(4) Integer Inches (in)	(5) Calculated Distance (ft-in)	(6) Inadvertent Movement Adder (ft)	(7) Table Distance (ft-in)
2.0	1.40	4.80	5	1- 5	1	2- 5
2.1	1.47	5.64	6	1- 6	1	2- 6
2.2	1.54	6.48	7	1- 7	1	2- 7
2.3	1.61	7.32	8	1- 8	1	2- 8
2.4	1.68	8.16	9	1- 9	1	2- 9
2.5	1.75	9.00	9	1- 9	1	2- 9
2.6	1.82	9.84	10	1-10	1	2-10
2.7	1.89	10.68	11	1-11	1	2-11
2.8	1.96	11.52	12	2- 0	1	3- 0
2.9	2.03	0.36	1	2- 1	1	3- 1
3.0	2.10	1.20	2	2- 2	1	3- 2

Where:

Column (1): Per-Unit Transient Overvoltage (TOV) range in accordance with the TABLE F, Column(2) explanation.

Column (2): Gap distance (IEEE Std 516-1987, Table 4).

Column (3): Decimal portion (ONLY) of Column (2) times 12 inches/foot equal decimal inches.

Column (4): Column (3) rounded in accordance with Rule 441A5a(1).

Column (5): Integer feet from Column (2) plus integer inches from (4).

Column (6): Inadvertent movement (ergonomic) adder in accordance with Rule 441A5a(3).

Column (7): Column (5) plus Column (6) in feet and inches equal values in Table 441-2 FT.

Column explanations are identical for TABLES N-1 through N-7.

145 kV, 2.0 through 3.0 pu Transient Overvoltage

TABLE N-2

(1) Per-Unit TOV	(2) Gap Distance (ft)	(3) Decimal Feet to Inches (in)	(4) Integer Inches (in)	(5) Calculated Distance (ft-in)	(6) Inadvertent Movement Adder (ft)	(7) Table Distance (ft-in)
2.0	1.70	8.40	9	1- 9	1	2- 9
2.1	1.79	9.48	10	1-10	1	2-10
2.2	1.87	10.44	11	1-11	1	2-11
2.3	1.96	11.52	12	2- 0	1	3- 0
2.4	2.04	0.48	1	2- 1	1	3- 1
2.5	2.13	1.56	2	2- 2	1	3- 2
2.6	2.21	2.52	3	2- 3	1	3- 3
2.7	2.30	3.60	4	2- 4	1	3- 4
2.8	2.38	4.56	5	2- 5	1	3- 5
2.9	2.47	5.64	6	2- 6	1	3- 6
3.0	2.55	6.60	7	2- 7	1	3- 7

169 kV, 2.0 through 3.0 pu Transient Overvoltage

TABLE N-3

(1) Per-Unit TOV	(2) Gap Distance (ft)	(3) Decimal Feet to Inches (in)	(4) Integer Inches (in)	(5) Calculated Distance (ft-in)	(6) Inadvertent Movement Adder (ft)	(7) Table Distance (ft-in)
2.0	2.00	0.00	0	2- 0	1	3- 0
2.1	2.10	1.20	2	2- 2	1	3- 2
2.2	2.20	2.40	3	2- 3	1	3- 3
2.3	2.30	3.60	4	2- 4	1	3- 4
2.4	2.40	4.80	5	2- 5	1	3- 5
2.5	2.50	6.00	6	2- 6	1	3- 6
2.6	2.60	7.20	8	2- 8	1	3- 8
2.7	2.70	8.40	9	2- 9	1	3- 9
2.8	2.80	9.60	10	2-10	1	3-10
2.9	2.90	10.80	11	2-11	1	3-11
3.0	3.00	0.00	0	3- 0	1	4- 0

242 kV, 2.0 through 3.0 pu Transient Overvoltage

TABLE N-4

(1) Per-Unit TOV	(2) Gap Distance (ft)	(3) Decimal Feet to Inches (in)	(4) Integer Inches (in)	(5) Calculated Distance (ft-in)	(6) Inadvertent Movement Adder (ft)	(7) Table Distance (ft-in)
2.0	2.80	9.60	10	2-10	1	3-10
2.1	2.94	11.28	12	3- 0	1	4- 0
2.2	3.08	0.96	1	3- 1	1	4- 1
2.3	3.22	2.64	3	3- 3	1	4- 3
2.4	3.35	4.20	5	3- 5	1	4- 5
2.5	3.50	6.00	6	3- 6	1	4- 6
2.6	3.64	7.68	8	3- 8	1	4- 8
2.7	3.76	9.12	10	3-10	1	4-10
2.8	3.92	11.04	11	3-11	1	4-11
2.9	4.05	0.60	1	4- 1	1	5- 1
3.0	4.20	2.40	3	4- 3	1	5- 3

362 kV, 2.0 through 3.0 pu Transient Overvoltage

TABLE N-5

(1) Per-Unit TOV	(2) Gap Distance (ft)	(3) Decimal Feet to Inches (in)	(4) Integer Inches (in)	(5) Calculated Distance (ft-in)	(6) Inadvertent Movement Adder (ft)	(7) Table Distance (ft-in)
2.0	4.20	2.40	3	4- 3	1	5- 3
2.1	4.41	4.92	5	4- 5	1	5- 5
2.2	4.70	8.40	9	4- 9	1	5- 9
2.3	5.01	0.12	1	5- 1	1	6- 1
2.4	5.34	4.08	4	5- 4	1	6- 4
2.5	5.67	8.04	8	5- 8	1	6- 8
2.6	6.01	0.12	1	6- 1	1	7- 1
2.7	6.36	4.32	5	6- 5	1	7- 5
2.8	6.73	8.76	9	6- 9	1	7- 9
2.9	7.10	1.20	2	7- 2	1	8- 2
3.0	7.48	5.76	6	7- 6	1	8- 6

550 kV, 1.5 through 2.4 pu Transient Overvoltage

TABLE N-6

(1) Per-Unit TOV	(2) Gap Distance (ft)	(3) Decimal Feet to Inches (in)	(4) Integer Inches (in)	(5) Calculated Distance (ft-in)	(6) Inadvertent Movement Adder (ft)	(7) Table Distance (ft-in)
1.5	4.97	11.64	12	5- 0	1	6- 0
1.6	5.46	5.52	6	5- 6	1	6- 6
1.7	5.98	11.76	12	6- 0	1	7- 0
1.8	6.51	6.12	7	6- 7	1	7- 7
1.9	7.08	0.96	1	7- 1	1	8- 1
2.0	7.68	8.16	9	7- 9	1	8- 9
2.1	8.27	3.24	4	8- 4	1	9- 4
2.2	8.87	10.44	11	8-11	1	9-11
2.3	9.49	5.88	6	9- 6	1	10- 6
2.4	10.21	2.52	3	10- 3	1	11- 3

800 kV, 1.5 through 2.0 pu Transient Overvoltage

TABLE N-7

(1) Per-Unit TOV	(2) Gap Distance (ft)	(3) Decimal Feet to Inches (in)	(4) Integer Inches (in)	(5) Calculated Distance (ft-in)	(6) Inadvertent Movement Adder (ft)	(7) Table Distance (ft-in)
1.5	8.66	7.92	8	8- 8	1	9- 8
1.6	9.60	7.20	8	9- 8	1	10- 8
1.7	10.60	7.20	8	10- 8	1	11- 8
1.8	11.64	7.68	8	11- 8	1	12- 8
1.9	12.73	8.76	9	12- 9	1	13- 9
2.0	13.86	10.32	11	13-11	1	14-11

**DERIVATION OF Table 441-2 M. AC PHASE-TO-GROUND
PER-UNIT DISTANCES IN METERS**

**Table 441-2 M
AC Live-Line Work Minimum Approach Distance
With Transient Overvoltage Factor**

Maximum Antici- pated Per-Unit Transient Over- Voltage	Distance to Employee In Meters, <u>Phase-To-Ground</u>						
	Air, Bare-Hand, and Clear Live-Line Tool						
	Maximum Phase-to-Phase Voltage In Kilovolts						
	<u>121</u>	<u>145</u>	<u>169</u>	<u>242</u>	<u>362</u>	<u>550</u>	<u>800</u>
1.5						1.82	2.95
1.6						1.97	3.23
1.7						2.13	3.54
1.8						2.29	3.86
1.9						2.47	4.19
2.0	0.74	0.83	0.92	1.16	1.59	2.65	4.53
2.1	0.76	0.85	0.95	<u>1.21</u>	1.65	2.83	
2.2	0.78	0.88	0.98	<u>1.25</u>	1.74	3.01	
2.3	0.80	0.91	1.01	1.29	1.84	3.20	
2.4	0.82	0.93	1.04	1.33	1.94	3.42	
2.5	0.84	0.96	1.07	1.38	2.04		
2.6	0.86	0.98	1.10	1.42	2.14		
2.7	0.88	1.01	1.13	1.45	2.25		
2.8	0.91	1.03	1.16	1.50	2.36		
2.9	0.93	1.06	1.19	1.54	2.47		
3.0	0.95	1.09	1.22	1.59	2.59		

121 KV, 2.0 through 3.0 pu Transient Overvoltage

TABLE O-1

(1) Per-Unit TOV	(2) Gap Distance (ft)	(3) Feet to Meters (m)	(4) Inadvertent Movement Adder (m)	(5) Calculated Distance (m)	(6) Table Distance (m)
2.0	1.40	0.4268	0.3048	0.7316	0.74
2.1	1.47	0.4481	0.3048	0.7529	0.76
2.2	1.54	0.4694	0.3048	0.7742	0.78
2.3	1.61	0.4908	0.3048	0.7956	0.80
2.4	1.68	0.5121	0.3048	0.8169	0.82
2.5	1.75	0.5334	0.3048	0.8382	0.84
2.6	1.82	0.5548	0.3048	0.8596	0.86
2.7	1.89	0.5761	0.3048	0.8809	0.88
2.8	1.96	0.5974	0.3048	0.9022	0.91
2.9	2.03	0.6188	0.3048	0.9236	0.93
3.0	2.10	0.6401	0.3048	0.9449	0.95

Where:

Column (1): Per-Unit Transient Overvoltage.

Column (2): Gap distance (See TABLES N, Column (2)). The metric tables are calculated from IEEE Std 516-1987, Table 4, english values rather than taking them from the metric tables of the standard. This was done for consistency and to avoid rounding redundancy.

Column (3): Feet to Meters equal Column (2) times 0.3048 meters/foot.

Column (4): Inadvertent movement (ergonomic) adder in accordance with Rule 441A5a(3).

Column (5): Column (3) plus Column (4).

Column (6): Column (5) rounded in accordance with Rule 441A5a(2) in meters equal values in Table 441-2 M.

Column explanations are identical for TABLES O-1 through O-7.

145 kV, 2.0 through 3.0 pu Transient Overvoltage

TABLE 0-2

(1) Per-Unit TOV	(2) Gap Distance (ft)	(3) Feet to Meters (m)	(4) Inadvertent Movement Adder (m)	(5) Calculated Distance (m)	(6) Table Distance (m)
2.0	1.70	0.5182	0.3048	0.8230	0.83
2.1	1.79	0.5456	0.3048	0.8504	0.85
2.2	1.87	0.5700	0.3048	0.8748	0.88
2.3	1.96	0.5974	0.3048	0.9022	0.91
2.4	2.04	0.6218	0.3048	0.9266	0.93
2.5	2.13	0.6493	0.3048	0.9541	0.96
2.6	2.21	0.6736	0.3048	0.9784	0.98
2.7	2.30	0.7011	0.3048	1.0059	1.01
2.8	2.38	0.7255	0.3048	1.0303	1.03
2.9	2.47	0.7529	0.3048	1.0577	1.06
3.0	2.55	0.7773	0.3048	1.0821	1.09

169 kV, 2.0 through 3.0 pu Transient Overvoltage

TABLE 0-3

(1) Per-Unit TOV	(2) Gap Distance (ft)	(3) Feet to Meters (m)	(4) Inadvertent Movement Adder (m)	(5) Calculated Distance (m)	(6) Table Distance (m)
2.0	2.00	0.6096	0.3048	0.9144	0.92
2.1	2.10	0.6401	0.3048	0.9449	0.95
2.2	2.20	0.6706	0.3048	0.9754	0.98
2.3	2.30	0.7011	0.3048	1.0059	1.01
2.4	2.40	0.7316	0.3048	1.0364	1.04
2.5	2.50	0.7620	0.3048	1.0668	1.07
2.6	2.60	0.7925	0.3048	1.0973	1.10
2.7	2.70	0.8230	0.3048	1.1278	1.13
2.8	2.80	0.8535	0.3048	1.1583	1.16
2.9	2.90	0.8840	0.3048	1.1888	1.19
3.0	3.00	0.9144	0.3048	1.2192	1.22

242 kV, 2.0 through 3.0 pu Transient Overvoltage

TABLE 0-4

(1) Per-Unit TOV	(2) Gap Distance (ft)	(3) Feet to Meters (m)	(4) Inadvertent Movement Adder (m)	(5) Calculated Distance (m)	(6) Table Distance (m)
2.0	2.80	0.8535	0.3048	1.1583	1.16
2.1	2.94	0.8962	0.3048	1.2010	1.21
2.2	3.08	0.9388	0.3048	1.2436	1.25
2.3	3.22	0.9815	0.3048	1.2863	1.29
2.4	3.35	1.0211	0.3048	1.3259	1.33
2.5	3.50	1.0668	0.3048	1.3716	1.38
2.6	3.64	1.1095	0.3048	1.4143	1.42
2.7	3.76	1.1461	0.3048	1.4509	1.45
2.8	3.92	1.1949	0.3048	1.4997	1.50
2.9	4.05	1.2345	0.3048	1.5393	1.54
3.0	4.20	1.2802	0.3048	1.5850	1.59

362 kV. 2.0 through 3.0 pu Transient Overvoltage

TABLE 0-5

(1) Per-Unit TOV	(2) Gap Distance (ft)	(3) Feet to Meters (m)	(4) Inadvertent Movement Adder (m)	(5) Calculated Distance (m)	(6) Table Distance (m)
2.0	4.20	1.2802	0.3048	1.5850	1.59
2.1	4.41	1.3442	0.3048	1.6490	1.65
2.2	4.70	1.4326	0.3048	1.7374	1.74
2.3	5.01	1.5271	0.3048	1.8319	1.84
2.4	5.34	1.6277	0.3048	1.9325	1.94
2.5	5.67	1.7283	0.3048	2.0331	2.04
2.6	6.01	1.8319	0.3048	2.1367	2.14
2.7	6.36	1.9386	0.3048	2.2434	2.25
2.8	6.73	2.0513	0.3048	2.3561	2.36
2.9	7.10	2.1641	0.3048	2.4689	2.47
3.0	7.48	2.2799	0.3048	2.5847	2.59

550 kV. 1.5 through 2.4 pu Transient Overvoltage

TABLE 0-6

(1) Per-Unit TOV	(2) Gap Distance (ft)	(3) Feet to Meters (m)	(4) Inadvertent Movement Adder (m)	(5) Calculated Distance (m)	(6) Table Distance (m)
1.5	4.97	1.5149	0.3048	1.8197	1.82
1.6	5.46	1.6642	0.3048	1.9690	1.97
1.7	5.98	1.8227	0.3048	2.1275	2.13
1.8	6.51	1.9843	0.3048	2.2891	2.29
1.9	7.08	2.1580	0.3048	2.4628	2.47
2.0	7.68	2.3409	0.3048	2.6457	2.65
2.1	8.27	2.5207	0.3048	2.8255	2.83
2.2	8.87	2.7036	0.3048	3.0084	3.01
2.3	9.49	2.8926	0.3048	3.1974	3.20
2.4	10.21	3.1120	0.3048	3.4168	3.42

800 kV. 1.5 through 2.0 pu Transient Overvoltage

TABLE 0-7

(1) Per-Unit TOV	(2) Gap Distance (ft)	(3) Feet to Meters (m)	(4) Inadvertent Movement Adder (m)	(5) Calculated Distance (m)	(6) Table Distance (m)
1.5	8.66	2.6396	0.3048	2.9444	2.95
1.6	9.60	2.9261	0.3048	3.2309	3.23
1.7	10.60	3.2309	0.3048	3.5357	3.54
1.8	11.64	3.5479	0.3048	3.8527	3.86
1.9	12.73	3.8801	0.3048	4.1849	4.19
2.0	13.86	4.2246	0.3048	4.5294	4.53

**DERIVATION OF Table 441-3 FT. AC PHASE-TO-PHASE
PER-UNIT DISTANCES IN FEET AND INCHES**

**Table 441-3 FT
AC Live-Line Work Minimum Approach Distance
With Transient Overvoltage Factor**

Maximum Anticipated Per-Unit Transient Over-Voltage	Distance to Employee In Feet-Inches, <u>Phase-To-Phase</u>						
	Air, Bare-Hand, and Clear Live-Line Tool						
	Maximum Phase-to-Phase Voltage In Kilovolts						
	<u>121</u>	<u>145</u>	<u>169</u>	<u>242</u>	<u>362</u>	<u>550</u>	<u>800</u>
1.5						7- 4	12- 1
1.6						8- 9	14- 6
1.7						10- 2	17- 2
1.8						11- 7	19-11
1.9						13- 2	22-11
2.0	3- 7	4- 1	4- 8	6- 1	8- 7	14-10	26- 0
2.1	3- 7	4- 2	4- 9	6- 3	8-10	15- 7	
2.1	3- 8	4- 3	4-10	6- 4	9- 2	16- 4	
2.3	3- 9	4- 4	4-11	6- 6	9- 6	17- 2	
2.4	3-10	4- 5	5- 0	6- 7	9-11	18- 1	
2.5	3-11	4- 6	5- 2	6- 9	10- 4		
2.6	4- 0	4- 7	5- 3	6-11	10- 9		
2.7	4- 1	4- 8	5- 4	7- 0	11- 2		
2.8	4- 1	4- 9	5- 5	7- 2	11- 7		
2.9	4- 2	4-10	5- 6	7- 4	12- 1		
3.0	4- 3	4-11	5- 8	7- 6	12- 6		

121 kV, 2.0 through 3.0 pu Transient Overvoltage

TABLE P-1

(1) Per-Unit TOV	(2) Gap Dist. (ft)	(3) Ratio (ft)	(4) Phase-to-Phase (ft)	(5) Decimal Feet to Inches (in)	(6) Integer Inches (in)	(7) Calculated Distance (ft-in)	(8) Inadvertent Movement Adder (ft)	(9) Table Distance (ft-in)
2.0	1.40	1.8000	2.5200	6.24	7	2- 7	1	3- 7
2.1	1.47	1.7619	2.5900	7.08	7	2- 7	1	3- 7
2.2	1.54	1.7273	2.6601	7.93	8	2- 8	1	3- 8
2.3	1.61	1.6957	2.7301	8.77	9	2- 9	1	3- 9
2.4	1.68	1.6667	2.8001	9.61	10	2-10	1	3-10
2.5	1.75	1.6400	2.8700	10.44	11	2-11	1	3-11
2.6	1.82	1.6154	2.9401	11.28	12	3- 0	1	4- 0
2.7	1.89	1.5926	3.0101	0.13	1	3- 1	1	4- 1
2.8	1.96	1.5715	3.0802	0.97	1	3- 1	1	4- 1
2.9	2.03	1.5518	3.1502	1.81	2	3- 2	1	4- 2
3.0	2.10	1.5334	3.2202	2.65	3	3- 3	1	4- 3

Where:

- Column (1): Per-Unit Transient Overvoltage (TOV) range in accordance with the TABLE F, Column (2) explanation.
- Column (2): Gap distance (See TABLES N, Column (2)).
- Column (3): Ratio multiplier from Table I.
- Column (4): Column (2) times Column (3).
- Column (5): Decimal portion (ONLY) of Column (4) in feet times 12 inches/foot equal decimal inches.
- Column (6): Column (5) rounded in accordance with Rule 441A5a(1).
- Column (7): Integer feet from Column (4) plus integer inches from Column (6).
- Column (8): Inadvertent movement (ergonomic) adder in accordance with Rule 441A5a(3).
- Column (9): Column (7) plus Column (8) in feet and inches equal values in Table 441-3 FT.

Column explanations are identical for TABLES P-1 through P-7.

145 kV, 2.0 through 3.0 pu Transient Overvoltage

TABLE P-2

(1) Per- Unit TOV	(2) Gap Dist. (ft)	(3) Ratio (ft)	(4) Phase -to- Phase (ft)	(5) Decimal Feet to Inches (in)	(6) Integer Inches (in)	(7) Calculated Distance (ft-in)	(8) Inadvertent Movement Adder (ft)	(9) Table Distance (ft-in)
2.0	1.70	1.8000	3.0600	0.72	1	3- 1	1	4- 1
2.1	1.79	1.7619	3.1538	1.85	2	3- 2	1	4- 2
2.2	1.87	1.7273	3.2301	2.77	3	3- 3	1	4- 3
2.3	1.96	1.6957	3.3236	3.89	4	3- 4	1	4- 4
2.4	2.04	1.6667	3.4001	4.81	5	3- 5	1	4- 5
2.5	2.13	1.6400	3.4932	5.92	6	3- 6	1	4- 6
2.6	2.21	1.6154	3.5701	6.85	7	3- 7	1	4- 7
2.7	2.30	1.5926	3.6630	7.96	8	3- 8	1	4- 8
2.8	2.38	1.5715	3.7402	8.89	9	3- 9	1	4- 9
2.9	2.47	1.5518	3.8330	10.00	10	3-10	1	4-10
3.0	2.55	1.5334	3.9102	10.93	11	3-11	1	4-11

169 kV, 2.0 through 3.0 pu Transient Overvoltage

TABLE P-3

(1) Per- Unit TOV	(2) Gap Dist. (ft)	(3) Ratio (ft)	(4) Phase -to- Phase (ft)	(5) Decimal Feet to Inches (in)	(6) Integer Inches (in)	(7) Calculated Distance (ft-in)	(8) Inadvertent Movement Adder (ft)	(9) Table Distance (ft-in)
2.0	2.00	1.8000	3.6000	7.20	8	3- 8	1	4- 8
2.1	2.10	1.7619	3.7000	8.40	9	3- 9	1	4- 9
2.2	2.20	1.7273	3.8001	9.61	10	3-10	1	4-10
2.3	2.30	1.6957	3.9002	10.81	11	3-11	1	4-11
2.4	2.40	1.6667	4.0001	0.01	0	4- 0	1	5- 0
2.5	2.50	1.6400	4.1000	1.20	2	4- 2	1	5- 2
2.6	2.60	1.6154	4.2001	2.41	3	4- 3	1	5- 3
2.7	2.70	1.5926	4.3001	3.61	4	4- 4	1	5- 4
2.8	2.80	1.5715	4.4002	4.81	5	4- 5	1	5- 5
2.9	2.90	1.5518	4.5003	6.01	6	4- 6	1	5- 6
3.0	3.00	1.5334	4.6002	7.21	8	4- 8	1	5- 8

242 kV, 2.0 through 3.0 pu Transient Overvoltage

TABLE P-4

(1) Per- Unit TOV	(2) Gap Dist. (ft)	(3) Ratio (ft)	(4) Phase -to- Phase (ft)	(5) Decimal Feet to Inches (in)	(6) Integer Inches (in)	(7) Calculated Distance (ft-in)	(8) Inadvertent Movement Adder (ft)	(9) Table Distance (ft-in)
2.0	2.80	1.8000	5.0400	0.48	1	5- 1	1	6- 1
2.1	2.94	1.7619	5.1800	2.16	3	5- 3	1	6- 3
2.2	3.08	1.7273	5.3201	3.85	4	5- 4	1	6- 4
2.3	3.22	1.6957	5.4602	5.53	6	5- 6	1	6- 6
2.4	3.35	1.6667	5.5835	7.01	7	5- 7	1	6- 7
2.5	3.50	1.6400	5.7400	8.88	9	5- 9	1	6- 9
2.6	3.64	1.6154	5.8801	10.57	11	5-11	1	6-11
2.7	3.76	1.5926	5.9882	11.86	12	6- 0	1	7- 0
2.8	3.92	1.5715	6.1603	1.93	2	6- 2	1	7- 2
2.9	4.05	1.5518	6.2848	3.42	4	6- 4	1	7- 4
3.0	4.20	1.5334	6.4403	5.29	6	6- 6	1	7- 6

362 kV, 2.0 through 3.0 pu Transient Overvoltage

TABLE P-5

(1) Per- Unit TOV	(2) Gap Dist. (ft)	(3) Ratio (ft)	(4) Phase -to- Phase (ft)	(5) Decimal Feet to Inches (in)	(6) Integer Inches (in)	(7) Calculated Distance (ft-in)	(8) Inadvertent Movement Adder (ft)	(9) Table Distance (ft-in)
2.0	4.20	1.8000	7.5600	6.72	7	7- 7	1	8- 7
2.1	4.41	1.7619	7.7700	9.24	10	7-10	1	8-10
2.2	4.70	1.7273	8.1184	1.42	2	8- 2	1	9- 2
2.3	5.01	1.6957	8.4955	5.95	6	8- 6	1	9- 6
2.4	5.34	1.6667	8.9002	10.81	11	8-11	1	9-11
2.5	5.67	1.6400	9.2988	3.59	4	9- 4	1	10- 4
2.6	6.01	1.6154	9.7086	8.51	9	9- 9	1	10- 9
2.7	6.36	1.5926	10.1290	1.55	2	10- 2	1	11- 2
2.8	6.73	1.5715	10.5762	6.92	7	10- 7	1	11- 7
2.9	7.10	1.5518	11.0178	0.22	1	11- 1	1	12- 1
3.0	7.48	1.5334	11.4699	5.64	6	11- 6	1	12- 6

550 kV, 1.5 through 2.4 pu Transient Overvoltage

TABLE P-6

(1) Per- Unit TOV	(2) Gap Dist. (ft)	(3) Ratio (ft)	(4) Phase -to- Phase (ft)	(5) Decimal Feet to Inches (in)	(6) Integer Inches (in)	(7) Calculated Distance (ft-in)	(8) Inadvertent Movement Adder (ft)	(9) Table Distance (ft-in)
1.5	4.97	1.2750	6.3368	4.05	4	6- 4	1	7- 4
1.6	5.46	1.4063	7.6784	8.14	9	7- 9	1	8- 9
1.7	5.98	1.5221	9.1022	1.23	2	9- 2	1	10- 2
1.8	6.51	1.6250	10.5788	6.95	7	10- 7	1	11- 7
1.9	7.08	1.7171	12.1571	1.89	2	12- 2	1	13- 2
2.0	7.68	1.8000	13.8240	9.89	10	13-10	1	14-10
2.1	8.27	1.7619	14.5710	6.86	7	14- 7	1	15- 7
2.2	8.87	1.7273	15.3212	3.86	4	15- 4	1	16- 4
2.3	9.49	1.6957	16.0922	1.11	2	16- 2	1	17- 2
2.4	10.21	1.6667	17.0170	0.21	1	17- 1	1	18- 1

800 kV, 1.5 through 2.0 pu Transient Overvoltage

TABLE P-7

(1) Per- Unit TOV	(2) Gap Dist. (ft)	(3) Ratio (ft)	(4) Phase -to- Phase (ft)	(5) Decimal Feet to Inches (in)	(6) Integer Inches (in)	(7) Calculated Distance (ft-in)	(8) Inadvertent Movement Adder (ft)	(9) Table Distance (ft-in)
1.5	8.66	1.2750	11.0415	0.50	1	11- 1	1	12- 1
1.6	9.60	1.4063	13.5005	6.01	6	13- 6	1	14- 6
1.7	10.60	1.5221	16.1343	1.62	2	16- 2	1	17- 2
1.8	11.64	1.6250	18.9150	10.98	11	18-11	1	19-11
1.9	12.73	1.7171	21.8587	10.31	11	21-11	1	22-11
2.0	13.86	1.8000	24.9480	11.38	12	25- 0	1	26- 0

**DERIVATION OF Table 441-3 M. AC PHASE-TO-PHASE
PER-UNIT DISTANCES IN METERS**

**Table 441-3 M
AC Live-Line Work Minimum Approach Distance
With Transient Overvoltage Factor**

Maximum Antici- pated Per-Unit Transient Over- Voltage	Distance to Employee In Meters, <u>Phase-To-Phase</u>						
	Air, Bare-Hand, and Clear Live-Line Tool						
	Maximum Phase-to-Phase Voltage In Kilovolts						
	<u>121</u>	<u>145</u>	<u>169</u>	<u>242</u>	<u>362</u>	<u>550</u>	<u>800</u>
1.5						2.24	3.67
1.6						2.65	4.42
1.7						3.08	5.23
1.8						3.53	6.07
1.9						4.01	6.97
2.0	1.08	1.24	1.41	1.85	2.61	4.52	7.91
2.1	1.10	1.27	1.44	1.89	2.68	4.75	
2.1	1.12	1.29	1.47	1.93	2.78	4.98	
2.3	1.14	1.32	1.50	1.97	2.90	5.21	
2.4	1.16	1.35	1.53	2.01	3.02	5.50	
2.5	1.18	1.37	1.56	2.06	3.14		
2.6	1.21	1.40	1.59	2.10	3.27		
2.7	1.23	1.43	1.62	2.13	3.40		
2.8	1.25	1.45	1.65	2.19	3.53		
2.9	1.27	1.48	1.68	2.22	3.67		
3.0	1.29	1.50	1.71	2.27	3.80		

121 kV, 2.0 through 3.0 pu Transient Overvoltage

TABLE Q-1

(1) Per-Unit TOV	(2) Gap Distance (ft)	(3) Feet to Meters (m)	(4) Inadvertent Movement Adder (m)	(5) Calculated Distance (m)	(6) Table Distance (m)
2.0	2.5200	0.7681	0.3048	1.0729	1.08
2.1	2.5900	0.7895	0.3048	1.0943	1.10
2.2	2.6601	0.8108	0.3048	1.1156	1.12
2.3	2.7301	0.8322	0.3048	1.1370	1.14
2.4	2.8001	0.8535	0.3048	1.1583	1.16
2.5	2.8700	0.8748	0.3048	1.1796	1.18
2.6	2.9401	0.8962	0.3048	1.2010	1.21
2.7	3.0101	0.9175	0.3048	1.2223	1.23
2.8	3.0802	0.9389	0.3048	1.2437	1.25
2.9	3.1502	0.9602	0.3048	1.2650	1.27
3.0	3.2202	0.9816	0.3048	1.2864	1.29

Where:

- Column (1): Per-Unit Transient Overvoltage (TOV) See TABLE F, Column(2)).
 Column (2): Gap phase-to-phase distance from TABLES P-1 through P-7, Column (4).
 Column (3): Column (2) times 0.3048 meters/foot.
 Column (4): Inadvertent movement (ergonomic) adder in accordance with Rule 441A5a(3).
 Column (5): Column (3) plus Column (4).
 Column (6): Column (5) rounded in accordance with Rule 441A5a(2) in meters equal values in Table 441-3 M.

Column explanations are identical for TABLES Q-1 through Q-7.

145 kV, 2.0 through 3.0 pu Transient Overvoltage

TABLE Q-2

(1) Per-Unit TOV	(2) Gap Distance (ft)	(3) Feet to Meters (m)	(4) Inadvertent Movement Adder (m)	(5) Calculated Distance (m)	(6) Table Distance (m)
2.0	3.0600	0.9327	0.3048	1.2375	1.24
2.1	3.1538	0.9613	0.3048	1.2661	1.27
2.2	3.2301	0.9846	0.3048	1.2894	1.29
2.3	3.3236	1.0131	0.3048	1.3179	1.32
2.4	3.4001	1.0364	0.3048	1.3412	1.35
2.5	3.4932	1.0648	0.3048	1.3696	1.37
2.6	3.5701	1.0882	0.3048	1.3930	1.40
2.7	3.6630	1.1165	0.3048	1.4213	1.43
2.8	3.7402	1.1401	0.3048	1.4449	1.45
2.9	3.8330	1.1683	0.3048	1.4731	1.48
3.0	3.9102	1.1919	0.3048	1.4967	1.50

169 kV, 2.0 through 3.0 pu Transient Overvoltage

TABLE Q-3

(1) Per-Unit TOV	(2) Gap Distance (ft)	(3) Feet to Meters (m)	(4) Inadvertent Movement Adder (m)	(5) Calculated Distance (m)	(6) Table Distance (m)
2.0	3.6000	1.0973	0.3048	1.4021	1.41
2.1	3.7000	1.1278	0.3048	1.4326	1.44
2.2	3.8001	1.1583	0.3048	1.4631	1.47
2.3	3.9002	1.1888	0.3048	1.4936	1.50
2.4	4.0001	1.2193	0.3048	1.5241	1.53
2.5	4.1000	1.2497	0.3048	1.5545	1.56
2.6	4.2001	1.2802	0.3048	1.5850	1.59
2.7	4.3001	1.3107	0.3048	1.6155	1.62
2.8	4.4002	1.3412	0.3048	1.6460	1.65
2.9	4.5003	1.3717	0.3048	1.6765	1.68
3.0	4.6002	1.4022	0.3048	1.7070	1.71

242 kV, 2.0 through 3.0 pu Transient Overvoltage

TABLE Q-4

(1) Per-Unit TOV	(2) Gap Distance (ft)	(3) Feet to Meters (m)	(4) Inadvertent Movement Adder (m)	(5) Calculated Distance (m)	(6) Table Distance (m)
2.0	5.0400	1.5362	0.3048	1.8410	1.85
2.1	5.1800	1.5789	0.3048	1.8837	1.89
2.2	5.3201	1.6216	0.3048	1.9264	1.93
2.3	5.4602	1.6643	0.3048	1.9691	1.97
2.4	5.5835	1.7019	0.3048	2.0067	2.01
2.5	5.7400	1.7496	0.3048	2.0544	2.06
2.6	5.8801	1.7923	0.3048	2.0971	2.10
2.7	5.9882	1.8252	0.3048	2.1300	2.13
2.8	6.1603	1.8777	0.3048	2.1825	2.19
2.9	6.2848	1.9156	0.3048	2.2204	2.22
3.0	6.4403	1.9630	0.3048	2.2678	2.27

362 kV, 2.0 through 3.0 pu Transient Overvoltage

TABLE Q-5

(1) Per-Unit TOV	(2) Gap Distance (ft)	(3) Feet to Meters (m)	(4) Inadvertent Movement Adder (m)	(5) Calculated Distance (m)	(6) Table Distance (m)
2.0	7.5600	2.3043	0.3048	2.6091	2.61
2.1	7.7700	2.3683	0.3048	2.6731	2.68
2.2	8.1184	2.4745	0.3048	2.7793	2.78
2.3	8.4955	2.5895	0.3048	2.8943	2.90
2.4	8.9002	2.7128	0.3048	3.0176	3.02
2.5	9.2988	2.8343	0.3048	3.1391	3.14
2.6	9.7086	2.9592	0.3048	3.2640	3.27
2.7	10.1290	3.0874	0.3048	3.3922	3.40
2.8	10.5762	3.2237	0.3048	3.5285	3.53
2.9	11.0178	3.3583	0.3048	3.6631	3.67
3.0	11.4699	3.4961	0.3048	3.8009	3.80

550 kV, 1.5 through 2.4 pu Transient Overvoltage

TABLE Q-6

(1) Per-Unit TOV	(2) Gap Distance (ft)	(3) Feet to Meters (m)	(4) Inadvertent Movement Adder (m)	(5) Calculated Distance (m)	(6) Table Distance (m)
1.5	6.3368	1.9315	0.3048	2.2363	2.24
1.6	7.6784	2.3404	0.3048	2.6452	2.65
1.7	9.1022	2.7744	0.3048	3.0792	3.08
1.8	10.5788	3.2245	0.3048	3.5293	3.53
1.9	12.1571	3.7055	0.3048	4.0103	4.01
2.0	13.8240	4.2136	0.3048	4.5184	4.52
2.1	14.5710	4.4413	0.3048	4.7461	4.75
2.2	15.3212	4.6699	0.3048	4.9747	4.98
2.3	16.0922	4.9049	0.3048	5.2097	5.21
2.4	17.0170	5.1868	0.3048	5.4916	5.50

800 kV, 1.5 through 2.0 pu Transient Overvoltage

TABLE Q-7

(1) Per-Unit TOV	(2) Gap Distance (ft)	(3) Feet to Meters (m)	(4) Inadvertent Movement Adder (m)	(5) Calculated Distance (m)	(6) Table Distance (m)
1.5	11.0415	3.3655	0.3048	3.6703	3.67
1.6	13.5005	4.1150	0.3048	4.4198	4.42
1.7	16.1343	4.9178	0.3048	5.2226	5.23
1.8	18.9150	5.7653	0.3048	6.0701	6.07
1.9	21.8587	6.6626	0.3048	6.9674	6.97
2.0	24.9480	7.6042	0.3048	7.9090	7.91

4. DERIVATION OF TABLE 441-4

The voltage ranges are DC conductor-to-ground as specified in ANSI Std C92.1-1982. The transient overvoltage ranges are from IEEE Transactions on Power Apparatus and Systems, Vol. PAS-96, No. 2, March/April 1977, pp. 591-601.

**DERIVATION OF Table 441-4 FT. DC CONDUCTOR-TO-GROUND
PER-UNIT DISTANCES IN FEET AND INCHES**

**Table 441-4 FT
DC Live-Line Work Minimum Approach Distance
With Transient Overvoltage Factor**

Maximum Anticipated Per-Unit Transient Overvoltage	Distance to Employee In Feet-Inches, Conductor To Ground				
	Air, Bare-Hand, and Clear Live-Line Tool				
	Maximum Conductor To Ground Voltage In Kilovolts				
	250	400	500	600	750
1.5 or lower	3- 8	5- 3	6- 9	8- 7	11-10
1.6	3-10	5- 7	7- 4	9- 5	13- 1
1.7	4- 1	6- 0	7-11	10- 3	14- 4
1.8	4- 3	6- 5	8- 7	11- 2	15- 9

250 kV DC, 1.5 through 1.8 pu Transient Overvoltage

TABLE R-1

(1) Per-Unit TOV	(2) Gap Distance (ft)	(3) Decimal Feet to Inches (in)	(4) Integer Inches (in)	(5) Calculated Distance (ft-in)	(6) Inadvertent Movement Adder (ft)	(7) Table Distance (ft-in)
1.5	2.66	7.92	8	2- 8	1	3- 8
1.6	2.83	9.96	10	2-10	1	3-10
1.7	3.01	0.12	1	3- 1	1	4- 1
1.8	3.19	2.28	3	3- 3	1	4- 3

Where:

- Column (1): Per-Unit Transient Overvoltage (TOV) (See TABLE F, Column(2)).
- Column (2): Gap distance (IEEE Std 516-1987, Table 5).
- Column (3): Decimal portion (ONLY) of Column (2) times 12 inches/foot equal decimal inches.
- Column (4): Column (3) rounded in accordance with Rule 441A5a(1).
- Column (5): Integer feet from Column (2) plus integer inches from Column (4).
- Column (6): Inadvertent movement (ergonomic) adder in accordance with Rule 441A5a(3).
- Column (7): Column (5) plus Column (6) in feet and inches equal values in Table 441-4 FT.

Column explanations are identical for TABLES R-1 through R-5.

400 kV DC, 1.5 through 1.8 pu Transient Overvoltage

TABLE R-2

(1) Per-Unit TOV	(2) Gap Distance (ft)	(3) Decimal Feet to Inches (in)	(4) Integer Inches (in)	(5) Calculated Distance (ft-in)	(6) Inadvertent Movement Adder (ft)	(7) Table Distance (ft-in)
1.5	4.24	2.88	3	4- 3	1	5- 3
1.6	4.53	6.36	7	4- 7	1	5- 7
1.7	4.95	11.40	12	5- 0	1	6- 0
1.8	5.40	4.80	5	5- 5	1	6- 5

500 kV DC, 1.5 through 1.8 pu Transient Overvoltage

TABLE R-3

(1) Per-Unit TOV	(2) Gap Distance (ft)	(3) Decimal Feet to Inches (in)	(4) Integer Inches (in)	(5) Calculated Distance (ft-in)	(6) Inadvertent Movement Adder (ft)	(7) Table Distance (ft-in)
1.5	5.73	8.76	9	5- 9	1	6- 9
1.6	6.34	4.08	4	6- 4	1	7- 4
1.7	6.91	10.92	11	6-11	1	7-11
1.8	7.57	6.84	7	7- 7	1	8- 7

600 kV DC, 1.5 through 1.8 pu Transient Overvoltage

TABLE R-4

(1) Per-Unit TOV	(2) Gap Distance (ft)	(3) Decimal Feet to Inches (in)	(4) Integer Inches (in)	(5) Calculated Distance (ft-in)	(6) Inadvertent Movement Adder (ft)	(7) Table Distance (ft-in)
1.5	7.57	6.84	7	7- 7	1	8- 7
1.6	8.38	4.56	5	8- 5	1	9- 5
1.7	9.23	2.76	3	9- 3	1	10- 3
1.8	10.11	1.32	2	10- 2	1	11- 2

750 kV DC, 1.5 through 1.8 pu Transient Overvoltage

TABLE R-5

(1) Per-Unit TOV	(2) Gap Distance (ft)	(3) Decimal Feet to Inches (in)	(4) Integer Inches (in)	(5) Calculated Distance (ft-in)	(6) Inadvertent Movement Adder (ft)	(7) Table Distance (ft-in)
1.5	10.82	9.84	10	10-10	1	11-10
1.6	12.05	0.60	1	12- 1	1	13- 1
1.7	13.34	4.08	4	13- 4	1	14- 4
1.8	14.70	8.40	9	14- 9	1	15- 9

**DERIVATION OF Table 441-4 M, DC CONDUCTOR-TO-GROUND
PER-UNIT DISTANCES IN METERS**

Table 441-4 M
DC Live-Line Work Minimum Approach Distance
With Transient Overvoltage Factor

Maximum Anticipated Per-Unit Transient Over- Voltage	Distance to Employee In Meters, <u>Conductor To Ground</u>				
	<u>Air, Bare-Hand, and Clear Live-Line Tool</u>				
	Maximum Conductor To Ground Voltage In Kilovolts				
	<u>250</u>	<u>400</u>	<u>500</u>	<u>600</u>	<u>750</u>
1.5 or lower	1.12	1.60	2.06	2.62	3.61
1.6	1.17	1.69	2.24	2.86	3.98
1.7	1.23	1.82	<u>2.42</u>	3.12	4.37
1.8	1.28	1.95	2.62	3.39	4.79

250 kV DC, 1.5 through 1.8 pu Transient Overvoltage

TABLE S-1

(1) Per-Unit TOV	(2) Gap Distance (ft)	(3) Feet to Meters (m)	(4) Inadvertent Movement Adder (m)	(5) Calculated Distance (m)	(6) Table Distance (m)
1.5	2.66	0.8108	0.3048	1.1156	1.12
1.6	2.83	0.8626	0.3048	1.1674	1.17
1.7	3.01	0.9175	0.3048	1.2223	1.23
1.8	3.19	0.9724	0.3048	1.2772	1.28

Where:

Column (1): Per-Unit Transient Overvoltage (TOV) (See TABLE F, Column (2)).

Column (2): Gap distance (See TABLES R, Column (2)).

Column (3): Feet to Meters equal Column (2) times 0.3048 meters/foot.

Column (4): Inadvertent movement (ergonomic) adder in accordance with Rule 441A5a(3).

Column (5): Column (3) plus Column (4).

Column (6): Column (5) rounded in accordance with Rule 441A5a(2) in meters equal values in Table 441-4 H.

Column explanations are identical for TABLES S-1 through S-5.

400 kV DC, 1.5 through 1.8 pu Transient Overvoltage

TABLE S-2

(1) Per-Unit TOV	(2) Gap Distance (ft)	(3) Feet to Meters (m)	(4) Inadvertent Movement Adder (m)	(5) Calculated Distance (m)	(6) Table Distance (m)
1.5	4.24	1.2924	0.3048	1.5972	1.60
1.6	4.53	1.3808	0.3048	1.6856	1.69
1.7	4.95	1.5088	0.3048	1.8136	1.82
1.8	5.40	1.6460	0.3048	1.9508	1.95

500 kV DC, 1.5 through 1.8 pu Transient Overvoltage

TABLE S-3

(1) Per-Unit TOV	(2) Gap Distance (ft)	(3) Feet to Meters (m)	(4) Inadvertent Movement Adder (m)	(5) Calculated Distance (m)	(6) Table Distance (m)
1.5	5.73	1.7465	0.3048	2.0513	2.06
1.6	6.34	1.9325	0.3048	2.2373	2.24
1.7	6.91	2.1062	0.3048	2.4110	2.42
1.8	7.57	2.3074	0.3048	2.6122	2.62

600 kV DC, 1.5 through 1.8 pu Transient Overvoltage

TABLE S-4

(1) Per-Unit TOV	(2) Gap Distance (ft)	(3) Feet to Meters (m)	(4) Inadvertent Movement Adder (m)	(5) Calculated Distance (m)	(6) Table Distance (m)
1.5	7.57	2.3074	0.3048	2.6122	2.62
1.6	8.38	2.5543	0.3048	2.8591	2.86
1.7	9.23	2.8133	0.3048	3.1181	3.12
1.8	10.11	3.0816	0.3048	3.3864	3.39

750 kV DC, 1.5 through 1.8 pu Transient Overvoltage

TABLE S-5

(1) Per-Unit TOV	(2) Gap Distance (ft)	(3) Feet to Meters (m)	(4) Inadvertent Movement Adder (m)	(5) Calculated Distance (m)	(6) Table Distance (m)
1.5	10.82	3.2980	0.3048	3.6028	3.61
1.6	12.05	3.6729	0.3048	3.9777	3.98
1.7	13.34	4.0661	0.3048	4.3709	4.37
1.8	14.70	4.4806	0.3048	4.7854	4.79

5. ALTITUDE CORRECTION

Table 441-5 is specified in IEEE Std 516-1987, Table 1. These multipliers are applied to the electrical component of the minimum approach distance (Rule 441A4). The inadvertent (ergonomic) adder from Rule 441A5a(3) should be subtracted from the table value, the altitude multiplier applied, and the inadvertent movement value reapplied (See EXAMPLE 1).

Table 441-5
Altitude Correction Factor

Altitude		Correction Factor
(ft)	(m)	
3,000	900	1.00
4,000	1,200	1.02
5,000	1,500	1.05
6,000	1,800	1.08
7,000	2,100	1.11
8,000	2,400	1.14
9,000	2,700	1.17
10,000	3,000	1.20
12,000	3,600	1.25
14,000	4,200	1.30
16,000	4,800	1.35
18,000	5,400	1.39
20,000	6,000	1.44

6. EXAMPLES**EXAMPLE 1****Application Of Altitude Correction**

Altitude correction is applied to the electrical component of the minimum approach distance listed in the tables minus the inadvertent movement (ergonomic) adder specified in Rule 441A5a(3). The user must decide whether to interpolate between altitudes or use the next higher altitude. The following example is chosen for an altitude listed in the table to avoid confusion.

Assume a 500 kV (maximum range 550 kV) transmission line at 8,000 feet altitude with a transient overvoltage of 2.0 per-unit.

- 1) The minimum approach distance from Table 441-2 for 550 kV with a 2.0 transient overvoltage is 8 foot 9 inches.
- 2) Converting feet and inches to decimal feet;
8 foot 9 inches = 8 + (9 inches/12 inches/foot) = 8.75 foot.
- 3) Subtracting 1 foot inadvertent movement adder (Rule 441A5a(3)), the number becomes;
8.75 foot - 1.0 foot = 7.75 foot.

- 4) Applying the altitude correction from Table 5 for 8,000 feet;
 $(7.75 \text{ foot})(1.14) = 8.835$ or 8.84 foot, rounding in accordance with Rule 441A5a(1).
- 5) Adding 1 inadvertent movement adder back in, the altitude corrected minimum approach distance is;
 $8.84 \text{ foot} + 1 \text{ foot} = 9.84 \text{ foot}.$
- 6) Converting decimal feet to inches;
 $9.84 \text{ foot} = 9 \text{ foot} + 0.84 \text{ foot};$
 $(0.84 \text{ foot})(12 \text{ inches/foot}) = 10.08 \text{ inches}$ or 10 inches when rounding in accordance with Rule 441A5a(1);
 or 9 foot 10 inches, an increase of 1 foot 1 inch.

For metric calculations use 1 foot = 0.3048 m and 2 foot = 0.6096 m for the parameters in this document.

AC phase-to-phase and DC conductor-to-ground minimum approach distances corrected for altitude are derived by the same method.

EXAMPLE 2
Use Of IEEE Std 516-1987 Minimum Approach Distance Equations
For A Voltage Not Listed In Tables 441-1 Through 441-3

Assume a 500 kV (maximum range 550 kV) transmission line has lost two parallel feeds (n-2 contingency) and the voltage has risen to 600 kV_{max} and the transient overvoltages will not exceed 2.2 per-unit under a live-line work order (hot line order). The minimum approach distance for this condition cannot be found in the tables and interpolation between table voltages is not permitted (Rule 441A5b). Calculations must be performed in accordance with Rule 441A5a(4) and the equations and criteria of IEEE Std 516-1987. The formulas and Figure 2 have been altered by changing S (maximum anticipated per-unit switching surge) to T (maximum anticipated per-unit transient overvoltage) to agree with the 1993 Edition of the NESC.

The equation from IEEE Std 516-1987, Paragraph 3.2.2.3, Minimum Approach Distance (Eq 2), is:

$$D = (C_1 C_2 + a)T(kV_{LG})$$

Where:

- D = Minimum Approach Distance,
- C₁ = 0.01, or one percent of V_{LG},
- C₂ = 1.0, (see text),
- a = saturation factor,
- T = maximum anticipated per-unit transient overvoltage, and
- kV_{LG} = rms system phase-to-ground kilovolts (maximum, not nominal).

Applying the example to the equation;

$$\begin{aligned} C_1 C_2 &= (0.01)(1.0) = 0.01, \\ T &= 2.2, \\ kV_{LG} &= (600 \text{ kV}_{max})/3^{1/2} = 347 \text{ kV}_{LG}, \\ a^6 &= 0.0032, \text{ and} \end{aligned}$$

$$D = (0.01 + 0.0032)(2.2)(347 \text{ kV}_{LG}) = 10.08 \text{ foot},$$

Adding 1 foot inadvertent movement (ergonomic) adder in accordance with Rule 441A5a(3), the minimum approach distance for altitudes 3000 feet and below is;

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Minimum Approach Distance} &= 10.08 \text{ foot} + 1 \text{ foot} = 11.08 \text{ foot, or} \\ 11 \text{ foot} + 0.08 \text{ foot} &= 11 \text{ foot} + (0.08 \text{ foot})(12 \text{ inches/foot}) = \\ 11 \text{ foot} + 0.96 \text{ inches, rounding in accordance with Rule 441A5a(1)} &= \\ 11 \text{ foot 1 inch} \end{aligned}$$

Example 1 calculations must be included for altitudes above 3000 feet.

⁶ The saturation factor "a" is calculated using V_{crest}. "a" may be taken directly from the graph in Figure 2 or it may be derived from the straight-line equations of Example 3. "a" for this example was derived from the straight-line equations of Example 3 with the following result:

$$kV_{crest} = (kV_{LG})(2^{1/2})S = (347 \text{ kV}_{LG})(2^{1/2})(2.2) = 1080 \text{ kV}_{crest}$$

$$a = (1080 - 640)/140000 = 0.0032$$

EXAMPLE 3
Straight-line Equations From
IEEE Std 516-1987 Fig 1
60 Hz Transient Overvoltage Saturation Factor

The following procedure may be used to derive the saturation factor used to calculate minimum approach distances using the equations from IEEE Std 516-1987. Values may differ slightly for the specific voltages listed in IEEE Std 516-1987 tables. The difference between reading "a" from the "best fit" curve of Figure 2 and the straight line equations presented here will have little effect on the calculated minimum approach distance. Rounding more than offsets the differences.

To derive equations from Figure 2, use "a" as the x-axis for a given V_{CREST} on the y-axis. Using straight line equations:

$$\text{Eq 1. } m = (y_2 - y_1)/(x_2 - x_1),$$

$$\text{Eq 2. } y = mx + b,$$

$$\text{Eq 2a. } b = y - mx, \text{ and}$$

$$\text{Eq 2b. } x = (y - b)/m,$$

and the two straight line equation intersect at or near $y = 1025$ kV and $x = 0.00275$, the equations for x ("a") become:

- A. For V_{CREST} greater than 1025 kV and selecting the points from the Figure 2 Graph $y_2 = 1305$ kV, $y_1 = 1025$ kV, $x_2 = 0.005$, and $x_1 = 0.00275$:

$$\text{(Eq 1) } m = (1305 - 1025)/(0.005 - 0.00275) = 124444 \text{ and}$$

$$\text{(Eq 2a) } b = 1305 - (124444)(0.005) = 683,$$

then, for any given V_{CREST} ,

$$\text{(Eq 2b) } a = (V_{CREST} - 683)/124444, \text{ and}$$

- B. For V_{CREST} less than 1025 kV and selecting the points from the Figure 1 Graph $y_2 = 1025$ kV, $y_1 = 780$ kV, $x_2 = 0.00275$, and $x_1 = 0.001$:

$$\text{(Eq 1) } m = (1025 - 780)/(0.00275 - 0.001) = 140000 \text{ and}$$

$$\text{(Eq 2a) } b = 1025 - (140000)(0.00275) = 640,$$

then, for any given V_{CREST} ,

$$\text{(Eq 2b) } a = (V_{CREST} - 640)/140000$$

7. FIGURES

FIGURE 1

Electric Power Research Institute (EPRI) Bluebook
Transmission Line Reference Book, 115-138 kV Compact Line Design
Section 5, Insulation For Switching Surges

EPRI - Figure 5.2
Approximate relationship of phase-to-phase
and phase-to-ground switching surges

FIGURE 2

IEEE Std 516-1987 Fig 1
Transient Overvoltage Saturation Factor

Note: "Switching Surge" from IEEE Std 516-1987 has been changed to "Transient Overvoltage" to agree with NESC-1993.